

International Workshop

"Globalization and Science in a Multipolar World"

Hybrid – online & in-person

April 26, 2024, Adelaide, AUSTRALIA

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i> <i>Navigating Globalization and Science in a Multipolar World: Perspectives and Prospects</i>	08.45-09.15
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i> <i>Globalization and Science in a Multipolar World: Challenges and Opportunities</i>	09.15-10.45 10.45-11.00
Q & A	
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Globalization in a Multipolar World</i> <i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i> <i>Globalization in a Multipolar World: Insights and Future Directions</i>	11.00-11.30
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i> <i>Globalization in a Multipolar World: Challenges, Insights, and Emerging Pathways</i>	11.30-12.00
<i>Session 2 – Science in a Multipolar World</i> <i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences Austria</i> <i>Navigating the Dynamics of Science in a Multipolar World:</i>	11.00-11.30

<p><i>Implications for Global Collaboration and Innovation</i></p> <p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Exploring the Complexities of Science in a Multipolar World: Challenges, Opportunities, and the Future of Global Collaboration and Innovation</i></p>	11.30-12.00
<p>Coffee break</p>	12.00-12.15
<p><i>Session 1 – Globalization in a Multipolar World</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Globalization in a Multipolar World: Navigating Shifting Power Dynamics, Regional Influences, and Emerging Global Paradigms</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Globalization in a Multipolar World: Analyzing the Interplay of Shifting Power Dynamics, Regional Influences, and the Evolution of Global Paradigms</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p><i>Session 2 – Science in a Multipolar World</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Science in a Multipolar World: Examining the Interactions of Global Knowledge Systems, Geopolitical Influence, and Collaborative Innovation</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Science in a Multipolar World: Investigating the Intersection of Global Knowledge Networks, Geopolitical Shifts, and the Future of Collaborative Innovation</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p>Q&A</p>	13.15-13.45
<p>Concluding remarks</p>	13.45-14.00

Location: Victoria Park, Level 3, 169 Fullarton Road, Dulwich, Adelaide, SA 5065, Australia